

INFLUENCE OF GENDER AND AGE ON PSYCHOSOCIAL ADJUSTMENT OF PEOPLE LIVING WITH HIV/AIDS IN CALABAR, NIGERIA

Akpabio, Idongesit I¹, Samson-Akpan, Patience E¹, Uyanah, D.A² and Osuchukwu, N. C³

¹Department of Nursing Science, University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross River State, ²Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Cross River University of Technology, Calabar Campus, Calabar, Cross River State, ³Department of Environmental Health, College of Medical Sciences, University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Purpose: Health and adjustment to chronic health conditions are often affected by various socio-demographic variables. This study assessed the influence of gender and age on the psychological, social and spiritual adjustment of people living with HIV/AIDS in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Materials and methods: A comparative descriptive research design was adopted to study 280 subjects selected from two health facilities within the study area. A validated adjustment questionnaire was the instrument for data collection while stratified random sampling involving balloting with replacement was used for sample selection.

Results: Results showed a significant influence of gender on the respondents' psychological, social and spiritual adjustment (Cal.t=7.89; 4.05; 3.78 > Crit.t=1.96). The males adjusted better than the females. Similarly, age of respondents exerted significant influence on psychological adjustment (Cal.F=5.54 > Crit.F.=2.37) but not on social and spiritual adjustment (Cal.F=1.67; 0.56 < Crit.F=2.37).

Recommendations: It is recommended that more HIV post-test counseling and health education on self-care be given to the female clients and the younger age groups taking their self-care needs as expressed by them into consideration.

KEYWORDS: Gender; Age; Psychosocial adjustment; HIV/AIDS; Counseling; Health-education; Self-care

INTRODUCTION

The HIV/AIDS' pandemic that has been in existence over twenty years has claimed over twenty million lives globally. An estimated 38 million people worldwide are living with HIV/AIDS; 25 million of these are in sub-Saharan Africa of whom 57% are women (Federal Ministry of Health, Nigeria, 2005). Additionally, according to the Federal Ministry of Health report, the first AIDS case in Nigeria was reported in 1986. Since then, the epidemic has steadily grown with a concomitant fall in life expectancy from 53 years in 1990 to 43.4 years in 2005, negating the positive effects that might have occurred as a result of improvements in life standards and health status.

The prevalence of HIV/AIDS in Nigeria, based on the 2005 sentinel report by GHAIN (2005) was 4.4%. This represented a slight decrease from 5.0% in 2003. GHAIN report also noted that about 249,000 new infections with HIV occurred in 2005. The prevalence is highest among young adults aged 25-29 years with 4.9%; closely followed by those aged 20-24 years (4.7%). It was further stated that HIV/AIDS' prevalence was highest in urban areas in twenty-six out of the thirty-six states of the federation. Nigeria, just like many other developing nations, suffers the formidable task of tackling a widespread epidemic, which has already claimed an estimated two million lives and left behind approximately, two million orphans. According to the estimate by the National Population Commission Nigeria (1999), a growing number of Nigerians (2.4 – 5.4 million) are people living with HIV and AIDS. Nearly all Nigerians are affected and having to face the many physical, social, financial and emotional problems that results from infection of a loved one. People living with HIV/AIDS are stigmatized and discriminated against. Additionally, due to the fact that AIDS has no total cure and could eventually result in death; many people also regard HIV as a death sentence.

Baylor International Paediatric AIDS' initiative (2003) observed that HIV transmission is often associated with violation of social norms regarding proper sexual relations. For this reason, people with HIV are often associated with having done something bad and therefore suffer psychological and social trauma. The issue of stigmatization attached to HIV/AIDS is still a major problem in many circles. AIDS' related discrimination impact negatively on the psychological and social adjustment of people living with HIV/AIDS. Some of the emotional responses experienced

by people living with HIV/AIDS have been similarly identified in people facing terminal illnesses. The individual goes through an initial stage of denial, anger, bargaining, depression and acceptance. Depression is increased by internalized shame over risky sexual behaviour and fear of stigmatization. Seeing many others become ill and experience alienation following AIDS increases the fear and depression. The individual could exhibit a variety of reactions such as depression with suicidal tendencies, hopelessness with a feeling that there is no reason to seek care for what is considered terminal illness.

Table 1: Gender and age of respondents (n=280)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender:		
Males	139	49.6
Females	141	50.4
Total	280	100%
Age in years:		
18 – 30	158	56.4
31 – 40	60	21.4
41 – 50	49	17.5
51 and above	13	4.6
Total	280	100%

Newman's theory of nursing focuses on the total person who is made up of physiological, socio-cultural and developmental variables (Kozier et al, 2004). The person is seen as having a range of lines of resistance to stressors which are unique to that person but within a common range with other human beings. Similarly, according to the health belief model, perception of illness is influenced by the individual's level of education, perceived threats of the illness and cues to action, which are all modified by various human characteristics such as age and gender (Basavanthappa, 2004).

Reporting on the poor psychosocial adjustment of women to HIV infection, the view by Basavanthappa is supported by Mishra (2005) who noted that in many developing countries, women were often economically, culturally and socially disadvantaged and lack access to treatment, financial support and education. Such limitations could therefore hinder their psychological adjustment to HIV/AIDS. Indeed, studies have shown that women with HIV/AIDS were at greater risk of psychological and psychiatric distress leading to disorganizing mental health disorders (Morrow et al, 2007; Busari and Danesy, 2004). Much of the data continue to point to a need for increasing psychosocial adjustment and support. In relation to age, it is noted that many young people are anxious and embarrassed about issues relating to sexual intercourse and HIV infection and could therefore have problem in adjusting psychosocially to HIV and AIDS. (Berman et al, 2008) On the other hand, the older age group who are bread winners could find it difficult to adjust psychologically and socially especially where their means of employment is affected or they are unable to provide the needed care and support to their family members. This view is supported by Berman et al (2008) who noted that individual's developmental level has a major impact on health status and to cope with stress.

Pace and Stables (1997); Meursing and Sibindi (2000) noted that patients with AIDS report significantly lower levels of spiritual wellbeing than patients with cancer and other chronic diseases. They also report greater feelings of loneliness and fewer support systems. According to the health locus of control model health and adjustment to ill health is largely self-determined based on variables including gender and age (Achal, 2001; American Nurses Association, 2004. Berman et al, 2008). This study therefore sought to ascertain the influence of gender and age on psychosocial (psychological, social and spiritual) adjustment of people living with HIV/AIDS in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Statement of research problem:

Working for health is concerned with understanding the meaning of health, the effects that deviation from health has on individuals from a range of perspectives, and factors, which enhance such effects. Additionally, it is also reported that in Cross River State, HIV/AIDS is prevalent among youths 20 – 29 years (4.7% - 4.9%). In respect to gender, Morrow et al, (2007), stated that the proportion of women with HIV infection had increased drastically in United States and accounted for 47% of all HIV/AIDS worldwide by the end of 2000. In Cross River State, the 2003 prevalence sentinel survey among pregnant women revealed a prevalence of 1 (Federal Ministry of Health, Nigeria, 2006).

Consequently, many strategies are being used in giving medical support to people living with AIDS. These approaches include organizing them into groups to access support from government and non-governmental

organizations on their health care needs. In Nigeria there is National Health Sector Strategic Plan for HIV and AIDS with guiding principles and purpose which show the highest level of political commitment to reduce morbidity and mortality associated with HIV/AIDS. This is also emphasized in the revised National Health Policy (Federal Ministry of Health, Nigeria, 2005).

Individuals who are diagnosed with HIV infection face great challenges in adapting to the reality of a subsequent disease that currently has no complete cure and for which there is only limited access to treatment in many parts of the world especially the developing countries of which Nigeria is one.

Table 2: Influence of gender on psychological, social and spiritual adjustment of people living with HIV/AIDS in Calabar, Cross River State (n = 280)

Variable	Gender	n	Mean	Std dev.	Df	't' value
Psychological Adjustment	Male	139	11.13	1.80	278	7.89
	Female	141	9.28	2.11		
	Total	280	10.20	2.17		
Social Adjustment	Male	139	11.01	1.64	278	4.05
	Female	141	10.10	2.09		
	Total	280	10.55	1.93		
Spiritual Adjustment	Male	139	11.67	0.89	278	3.78
	Female	141	11.10	1.55		
	Total	280	11.38	1.30		

Crit. t = 1.96; p = 0.05

The psychological trauma experienced by people living with HIV/AIDS is worrisome. Furthermore, the physical effect of HIV/AIDS and more importantly the social and economic impact is extended to loved ones and the community as a whole. Although advances in drug treatment are delaying the onset of AIDS for people infected with HIV and are providing new hope for them, the negative impact of stigmatization and fear of death has remained a vital source of psychological and social problems among people living with HIV/AIDS. This study therefore sought to highlight the psychological, social and spiritual adjustment of clients to HIV/AIDS' infection and to assess if their adjustment was influenced by their gender and age. This is necessary so as to tailor interventions to meet the psychosocial adjustment of the various groups to HIV infection.

Purpose of the study:

This study was conducted to determine the influence of gender and age on the psychological, social and spiritual adjustment of people living with HIV/AIDS. Consequently, the result could provide the care givers (health workers) the needed information to plan psychosocial adjustment programmes based on the needs of the various groups of respondents.

Specific objectives:

- To ascertain the differences between male and female respondents in their psychological, social and spiritual adjustment to HIV/AIDS.
- To identify the influence of age on the psychological, social and spiritual adjustment among people living with HIV/AIDS.

Hypotheses:

- There is no significant difference between males and females in their psychological, social and spiritual adjustment to HIV/AIDS.
- Age will have no significant influence on the psychological, social and spiritual adjustment among people living with HIV/AIDS.
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MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study adopted a comparative design to determine the psychological, social and spiritual adjustments of different groups with regards to gender and age. The study setting was Calabar, which consist of two Local Government Areas, Calabar South and Calabar Municipality. Calabar which is the capital of Cross River State, Nigeria could be described as having both an urban and sub-urban setting.

Calabar residents are mostly civil servants. There are two tertiary institutions – University of Calabar and Calabar campus of Cross River University of Technology. Industrial institutions include United Cement Company, Flour Mill, Nigerian Port Authority, Federal Government Parastatals and Banks which contribute to the economic life wire of the state. It is a tourist area where people are attracted to especially during the festive periods – Easter and Christmas and this has great implication for the spread of HIV/AIDS.

There are many health facilities in Calabar including University of Calabar Teaching Hospital, General Hospital, Infectious Disease Hospital and other Government owned hospitals and Health Centres including Private Clinics. There are also many health facilities where people living with HIV/AIDS consult for their regular care. These include both Government owned facilities and non governmental organizations with up to 74 facilities located in Calabar.

The target population included 16,350 people living with HIV/AIDS in Calabar Cross River State. This figure was derived from calculating 15% [18] of the 6.1% of the population estimated to be living with HIV/AIDS in Cross River State. 15% gave an estimate of 16,350 people living with HIV/AIDS in Calabar. According to Araoye (2004), where the population of a specific group is unknown, an estimate could be made using 15% of the available relevant population. Thus from a population of 2,873,000, the estimated 6.1% population translate to 109,800 PLWHA in Cross River State.

Table 3: Results of one-way ANOVA of psychological, social and spiritual adjustments by age group (n = 280)

Variable	Group	N	Mean	SD
Psychological Adjustment	18-30	58	9.84	2.32
	31-40	60	10.20	1.67
	41 – 50	49	11.02	2.04
	51 and above	13	11.46	1.66
	Total	280	10.20	2.17
Social adjustment	18-30	158	10.34	2.10
	31-40	60	10.67	1.54
	41-50	49	10.96	1.76
	51 and above	13	11.00	1.73
	Total	280	10.55	1.93
Spiritual adjustment	18-30	158	11.28	1.41
	31-40	60	11.50	0.79
	41-50	49	11.51	1.29
	51 and above	13	11.54	1.66
	Total	280	11.38	1.29

Variable	Sources of variation	Sum of squares	Df	Ms	F
Psychological Adjustment	Age	74.67	3	24.89	5.54
	Error	1239.53	276		
	Total	1314.20	279		
Social adjustment	Age	18.50	3	6.17	1.67
	Error	1016.80	276	3.68	
	Total	1035.30	279		
Spiritual adjustment	Age	3.45	3	1.15	0.563
	Error	464.66	276	1.68	
	Total	468.11	279		

The accessible population consisted of PLWHA who received care in two randomly selected health facilities in Calabar Cross River State. For 2007/2008, these included 3,218 from General Hospital, Calabar and 5,640 from University of Calabar Teaching Hospital, with a total of 8,858 from the two institutions. Two hundred and eighty (280) respondents were selected through stratified random sampling involving balloting and replacement method on four clinic days from each of the two selected health facilities. Data collection lasted for a period of two weeks.

The instrument for data collection was the validated questionnaire developed by the authors. Face validity was ascertained by colleagues in the Department of Nursing Science. Content Validity index score was .92 while

Cronbach's alpha reliability result was .94. This indicated a high level of reliability of the instrument to be used in the study.

The authors and trained health personnel who were care givers assisted in the collection of data. Informed consent was obtained from the respondents after due explanation of the intent of the study. Confidentiality was ensured through their being instructed not to write their names. The subjects were also given the option of willingly participating in the study or refusing to do so if they so desired. Written permission was also obtained from the two health institutions involved in the study prior to data collection.

The questionnaires were administered through face-to-face interaction between the researchers and the respondents, and on the spot retrieval of completed questionnaire.

The descriptive data on gender and age were analyzed using simple proportion of frequencies and percentages while t-test and analysis of variance were used for the testing of hypotheses. Results were presented in Tables.

RESULTS

The socio-demographic variables of respondents are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 shows that 141 (50.4%) of the subjects were females while 139 (49.6%) were males. Majority of the respondents 158 (56.4%) were aged 18-30 years.

Table 4: Fishers Post Hoc (LSD) multiple comparison test for significance of age on psychological adjustment (n = 280)

Age	1	2	3	4
18-30 1	155 9.84	60	49	13
31 – 40 2	1.13	10.20	0.82	1.26
41 – 50 3	3.43*	2.01*	11.03	-0.44
51 & above 4	2.66*	1.94	0.67	10.20

* Significant at 0.05 level. MSW = 4.49 Critical t = 1.96

Hypothesis I:

Test of significant difference between males and females in their psychological, social and spiritual adjustment to HIV/AIDS. The independent variables in this hypothesis are gender, while psychological, social and spiritual adjustments are dependent variables. To test this hypothesis, independent 't' test analysis was done. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 shows mean and standard deviation for males and female respondents. It also shows that for the three dependent variables psychological, social and spiritual adjustments, the corresponding calculated t values (7.89 for psychological, 4.05 for social adjustment and 3.78 for spiritual adjustments) are each greater than the critical 't' value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance when the degree of freedom is 278. With these results, the null hypothesis is not supported in each of the three types of adjustments. This means that gender has a significant influence on the psychological, social and spiritual adjustment of people living with HIV/AIDS. In all, as shown in Table 2, males are consistently more psychologically, socially and spiritually adjusted (mean = 11.14; 11.01 and 11.67) than females (mean = 9.28, 10.10 and 11.10) respectively.

Hypothesis 2:

This hypothesis stated that age will have no significant influence on the psychological, social and spiritual adjustment among people living with HIV/AIDS. The independent variable in this hypothesis is age and there are three dependent variables – psychological, social and spiritual adjustments. To test, this hypothesis, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out using SPSS version 7.5 with F-ratio and Fisher's LSD multiple comparison test to test for significance of influence of age on the dependent variables. Table 3 is a summary of the results.

The results in the upper part of Table 3 shows the sample size, means and standard deviation of the respondents based on their age group for the three dependent variables – psychological social and spiritual adjustments. The ANOVA results of the influence of age on the lower part of Table 3 show that for psychological adjustment, the calculated F-value (5.54) is greater than the critical F-value (2.37). Consequently, the null hypothesis is not supported. For social

and spiritual adjustments; the calculated F-values (1.67 and 0.56 respectively) are not greater than their corresponding critical F-value. The null hypothesis concerning the influence of age on social and spiritual adjustment was therefore supported. This means that age of respondents does not exert a significant influence on the social and spiritual adjustment of people living with HIV/AIDS.

To find out which age group was responsible for the significance of the ANOVA on psychological adjustment, the Fisher's LSD Post-Hoc, multiple comparison tests was carried out. The results are presented in Table 4.

The results in Table 4 show that age group 31 – 40 (mean = 10.20) is different from age group 18 – 30 (mean = 9.84) but not significantly ($t=1.13 < 1.96$). Age group 41-50 (mean = 11.03, $t = 3.43 > 1.96$); age group 50 and above (mean = 11.46, $t = 2.66 > 1.96$) are significantly different from age group 18-30 (mean = 9.84; $t = 2.66 > 1.96$). Age group 41-50 is also significantly different from age group 51 and above ($t = 2.01 > 1.96$). This means that the higher the age, the better the psychological adjustment.

On the other hand, in relation to social and spiritual adjustment of the respondents, since the calculated t-values obtained in each of the age groups are not higher than the critical 'F' values, no further analysis was done on social and spiritual adjustments.

In Table 4, group means are placed along the diagonal; differences between means are placed above the diagonal while Fisher's t-values are placed below the diagonal.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The result of the first hypothesis showed that gender had significant influence on the psychological, social and spiritual adjustment of people living with HIV/AIDS. The result also revealed that males were consistently more psychologically, socially and spiritually adjusted than females. Thus, the impact of HIV/AIDS on women is particularly worthy of note as posited by Mishra (2005) that in many developing countries women are often economically, culturally and socially disadvantaged and lack access to treatment, financial support and education. In a number of societies women are mistakenly perceived as the main transmitter of sexually transmitted diseases. Furthermore, the traditional beliefs about transmission of HIV/AIDS through promiscuous sexual behaviour provide a basis for further stigmatization of women and could be a basis for their poor psychosocial adjustment to HIV/AIDS.

Indeed, HIV-positive women are treated differently from men in many parts of the developing countries. Men are likely to be 'excused' in cases where they keep multiple sexual partners that could in many instances result in their infection. Women whose husbands have died from AIDS-related infection have been blamed for their husbands' death (Morrow, Costello and Boland) even though it could be obvious that they acquired the infection from their husbands. Studies have also shown that women worry more about the impact of their illnesses as well as those on their loved ones (Mishra, 2005). Additionally, economic stress and the burden of pregnancy and child rearing further add to their problems in cases of HIV infection (American Nurses Association, 2004; Busari and Danesy, 2004).. According to Federal Ministry of Health, Nigeria (2005), men as the head of the family take decisions usually as they favour them, and females are expected to be emotional and very sensitive to the needs of men. Women are not expected to express any negative feelings no matter the situation especially where men are concerned. In view of the vulnerability of women to physical, emotional and psychological abuse, it is therefore not surprising that they showed poor psychological, social and spiritual adjustment to the impact of HIV/AIDS.

In a similar dimension, Morrow et al, (2007) had engaged women with HIV disease in a qualitative need assessment for psychological services. The results supported the development of psychosocial support group especially for women with HIV infection and AIDS. In view of the fact that women are more vulnerable to poor psychological, social and spiritual adjustment to HIV/AIDS than men and it is likely that more women are now infected than men it becomes necessary to address HIV/AIDS' psychosocial problems with more emphasis on ensuring stability among the women.

The result further showed that age of respondents, had significant influence on their psychological adjustment to HIV infection and AIDS while for social and spiritual adjustment, age did not exert significant influence on these variables. The result indicated that the higher the age, the better the psychological adjustment. This result is in consonant with the fact that the perception of illness is influenced and modified by demographic characteristics including age (Achal, 2001; Basavanthappa, 2004) From the result, it was apparent that the young age groups 20 - 29 are mostly affected probably due to their inexperience on how to deal with life situations. This findings has implications for more attention on meeting the health care and emotional needs of the younger age group who are incidentally said to have the highest number of those infected with HIV (GHAIN, 2005)

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Gender had significant influence on psychological, social and spiritual adjustment of people living with HIV/AIDS in Calabar, Nigeria. Males were more adjusted with the three adjustment variables than females. Age only exerted significant influence on psychosocial adjustment. Additionally, it was observed that the higher the age, the better the psychological, social and spiritual adjustment of the respondents to HIV/AIDS.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study findings, it is recommended that in caring for people living with HIV/AIDS, their unique characteristics should be considered. More attention should be focused on the females' gender and younger age groups. More support in the form of post-test counseling and health education on self care should be given to them on a more regular basis. Such counseling and educational interventions should take their self care needs, as expressed by them into consideration. Furthermore, different support groups that are relevant to their developmental stages, social and spiritual background, as well as economic status should be encouraged. Since individuals with different age groups and gender adjust differently in terms of psychological, social and spiritual adjustment variables, having a mixed support group for all the different groups may not be adequate or effective in meeting their psychological, social and spiritual adjustment to HIV infection and AIDS.

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Received for Publication: 07/11/2008

Accepted for Publication: 12/12/2008

Corresponding Author:

Akpabio, Idongesit I

Department of Nursing Science, University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria.